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SPEARHEAD's Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Plan

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Executive Summary

The *SP*Ecification, *A*nalysis & *R*e-calibration of *H*igh Energy *p*Article *D*ata (**SPEARHEAD**) project plans to leverage very-high-energy particle observations from the most important heliophysics missions and ground-based measurements to answer key questions related to particles and solar eruptions. The project will develop innovative solutions to derive high-energy particle fluxes from observations, improve the use of monitoring data and enhance the analysis of solar eruptions. This *Dissemination and Communication Plan* outlines the expected results of the **SPEARHEAD** project and presents the first version of a detailed plan for their dissemination and communication to key target audiences. In detail, we have identified the following six main Key Target Groups of the project:

- T1.** Heliophysics community
- T2.** Astrophysics community
- T3.** Space weather community
- T4.** Undergraduate and PhD students
- T5.** Space Agencies and policymakers
- T6.** The General public

Each of the target groups will be addressed by tailored communication measures.

The plan will be a *living document* which will be updated over the project for each of the periodic reviews and the final review

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1 Introduction

The *SP*ecification, *AN*alysis & *RE*-calibration of *High Energy p*Article *D*ata (**SPEARHEAD**) project is funded under the Horizon Europe programme of the European Union (EU). The project focuses on high energy particles, originating either from the Sun (i.e., *Solar Energetic Particles* – **SEPs**) or our Galaxy (*Galactic Cosmic Rays* – **GCRs**). **SPEARHEAD** will address several open scientific questions on the acceleration, release and propagation physical processes of such particles. In doing so, **SPEARHEAD** provides novel high-level data products based on re-calibrations of radiation monitor data -- on so-far unreleased data from science-grade instruments, and measurements of ground-based neutron monitors; technical notes on the response functions of several science-grade and monitoring instruments, utilising Geant4 modelling; comprehensive catalogues of near-relativistic ions and relativistic electrons in strong SEP events as well as Forbush decrease (FD) events from a fleet of different instruments onboard spacecraft, at radial distances from 0.04 to 5 AU; scientific and data analysis as well as tools enabling the coordinated analysis of high energy particle data with contexts observations.

This document provides the *Dissemination and Communication Plan* of the Project. The purpose of the plan is to detail the Project's approach on what needs to be communicated and why, to whom, when, how, and by whom.

2 Expected results of the project

SPEARHEAD will deliver, validate, and distribute new high-level data of high energy particle intensities for the community through our own servers as well as through ESA and NASA archives and platforms (*ESA/Datalabs*) to the whole heliophysics and space weather research communities.

In addition to developing tools and data products for high-energy particles, the team will analyse energetic particle events and their relations to solar parameters such as X-ray flare peak flux and location, magnetic connectivity to the eruption site, parameters of the coronal mass ejection (CME) and the waves driven by them in regions magnetically connected to the observing spacecraft, etc.

The scientific objective of SPEARHEAD is to provide answers to the following science questions:

SQ1: How are ions and electrons accelerated to the highest energies in solar eruptions, beyond 100 MeV/n and 1 MeV, respectively?

SQ2: What are the processes governing particle release from acceleration sites in the solar corona?

SQ3: What are the key processes of high-energy particle transport in the interplanetary medium, in the magnetosphere and in the atmosphere?

Related to the science questions, the main technical objectives of SPEARHEAD are:

TO1: to develop and distribute analysis tools to extract high-energy particle fluxes from particle detectors designed to operate at lower energies or to yield monitoring data. Response functions of spacecraft instruments will be determined and particle fluxes of the very high energy particles as a function of time and energy will be delivered.

TO2: to process and cross-calibrate a large number of data to produce high-energy particle flux datasets and distribute them to the community.

TO3: to validate the data against intermittent direct spectrometer observations.

In summary, the anticipated results of the **SPEARHEAD** project can be grouped in three different output types:

- **Science:** The project is expected to arrive in enhanced understanding of fundamental physical processes of high-energy particle release acceleration and transport in the corona and the heliosphere. The focus is on near-relativistic ions and relativistic electrons, along with solar and interplanetary context observations.
- **Data and tools:** We provide high-level datasets on high-energy particles that have never before been available to the community, together with methodology for obtaining further science results utilising the datasets. The possibilities for further analysis of the data and visualization of the simulation output are provided as Jupyter Notebooks distributed via Jupyter Hub established in the project.
- **Outreach and educational material:** Sharing the results with the public and the next generation of researchers.

3 Key Target Groups and foreseen impact of the project

We have identified the following six main Key Target Groups for SPEARHEAD:

- T1. *Heliophysics community*:** Heliophysics studies the Sun and its effects on the Solar System; it addresses problems that span a number of research disciplines: solar and heliospheric physics, and magnetospheric, geophysics and ionospheric physics for the Earth and other planets. Solar energetic particles are a topic of interest to nearly all of these disciplines, for some on their own and for others through their effects on the systems under study. The heliophysics community includes both researchers and tool developers, like the Python in Heliophysics Community (PyHC).
- T2. *Astrophysics community*:** Particle acceleration and transport in electromagnetic fields are fundamental problems of astrophysics that can be studied experimentally using observations of solar eruptions and measurements of particle fluxes. Focusing our efforts on the highest energies of the solar particle spectrum will expand the range of energies presently covered by spacecraft measurements and studied in currently running projects such as H2020/SERPENTINE. Moreover, extreme events at the Sun also assess the Sun-like stars' ability to accelerate particles, which is an important topic of interest e.g. in studying the habitability of exoplanets. Finally, the modeling of propagating structures in the solar wind and their effect on GCRs directly addresses fundamentals of particle transport providing necessary constraints to our current knowledge.
- T3. *Space weather community*:** SEP events are among the most important phenomena of interest in the applied science of Space Weather research. This community includes both scientists and developers of software tools for predicting the space environment as well as engineers designing and planning space missions. **SPEARHEAD** tools for the analysis, the novel data sets that extend to high energies, results on SEP event properties at the highest energies and reconstructions of CMEs affecting GCRs near Earth and Mars can be exploited in future space weather prediction methodology and space radiation environment assessment models as well as for designing future space missions.
- T4. *Undergraduate and PhD students*:** SEP/GLE and FD events as well as space environment in general constitute topics of a large number of thesis projects of physics and astronomy in Europe and internationally. Thereby, analysis tools and new high-level data products provided by **SPEARHEAD** will directly facilitate PhD students in their work. More broadly, solar eruptions and their different manifestations are key topics of university courses on Solar physics, Heliospheric physics and Space physics. Particle acceleration and transport are typical elements of graduate-level courses in Astrophysics or Cosmic Rays.
- T5. *Space Agencies and policymakers*:** Heliophysics is one of the key programme elements in large national and international space agencies like ESA and NASA. These Agencies also maintain heliophysics data archives and platforms for analysis tools. Policymakers include the EU as well as national agencies and ministries responsible for funding research, innovation, technology development and also things like preparedness.
- T6. *The General public*:** Solar eruptions with their spectacular imaging observations and their capability to initiate aurorae are fascinating and popular topics to the broad public. This target group also includes school children and teachers. Also, the more adverse effects of space weather are of great interest to the public.

Table 3-1 below characterizes the foreseen impact of SPEARHEAD to each of the target groups.

Table 3-1: Overview of SPEARHEAD output, key target groups and foreseen impact

Output	Target group	Foreseen impact
<i>SPEARHEAD Science</i>	T1. Heliophysics community	<p>New knowledge on SEP events at high energies.</p> <p>New knowledge on FD events recorded within the heliosphere.</p> <p>Open science questions for planning new heliophysics missions and instrumentation, which may not be answered by the present missions.</p>
	T2. Astrophysics community	<p>Fundamental new knowledge on particle acceleration and transport.</p> <p>New knowledge on the radiation environment around sun-like stars.</p>
	T3. Space weather community	<p>New knowledge on the properties of SEP events.</p> <p>Reconstruction of the properties of interplanetary CME impacting GCRs at Earth and other planets (i.e. Mars)</p> <p>Strengthened scientific basis for service products on space weather.</p>
	T5. Space Agencies	<p>Increased scientific output from the inner heliospheric missions.</p> <p>Proposals for new mission and instrument concepts to observe SEPs at the highest energies and GCRs at different vantage points.</p>
<i>SPEARHEAD produced data and tools</i>	T1.Heliophysics community	<p>New data and analysis tools for investigating SEP events.</p> <p>New analysis platforms for easy data access and visualisation.</p> <p>Solar event catalogues and databases for statistical studies of energetic eruptions.</p>
	T3. Space weather community	<p>New data for constructing service products for the assessment of interplanetary radiation environments.</p> <p>High-level data products for validating space weather forecasting models.</p>
	T4. University students	<p>New data and analysis tools for investigating SEP/GLE and FD events. Event catalogues for statistical studies of SEP and FD events. (PhD level)</p> <p>New analysis platforms for easy data access and visualisation.</p>
	T5. Space Agencies	<p>New and improved datasets ingested to science</p>

		<p>archives. Tools for distribution along with the data.</p> <p>Improved knowledge on the interplanetary radiation environment affecting missions like ATHENA and LISA.</p>
<i>Outreach and educational material</i>	T4. University students	New learning material on solar eruptions. (PhD and undergraduate level)
	T6. General public	<p>Increased awareness, interest and recognition of European space science activities in general and heliospheric missions in particular.</p> <p>Interesting information about solar activity and its manifestations in the heliosphere.</p>

4 Dissemination of results

Dissemination of scientific results in **SPEARHEAD** will rely on the top-tier refereed journals of the field (e.g., *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, *Astrophysical Journal*, *Solar Physics*, *Journal of Space Weather and Space Climate*, *Journal of Geophysical Research*), but high-impact journals (e.g., *Science*, *Nature*, *Nature Astronomy*, *Nature Geophysics* and *Nature Communications*) will be considered as well for results that have broader geophysical or astrophysical impact. An Open Access option will be selected either by opting for Gold Access or self-archiving at arXiv.org (Green Access). The main astrophysical abstract database, Astrophysics Data System (**ADS**) of NASA, ingests all abstracts submitted to arXiv.org so even the Green Access option gives an easy open access to the results. Furthermore a Zenodo community has been created (<https://zenodo.org/communities/spearhead/>). It will facilitate the dissemination of results and will further serve for versioning (see D1.2 & D6.1)

The results will also be actively presented in:

1. established conferences of the field, e.g., General Assemblies of the *European Geosciences Union (EGU)*; *American Geophysical Union (AGU)*, *Committee on Space Research (COSPAR)*, *European Solar Physics Meeting (ESPM)*; *European Space Weather Week (ESWW)*, *International Cosmic Ray Conference (ICRC)*; *European Cosmic Ray Symposium (ECRS)*; *International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics (IUGG)* / *International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy (IAGA)*; *Solar Heliospheric and INterplanetary Environment (SHINE)*; *Scientific Committee on Solar-Terrestrial Physics (SCOSTEP)*, *Data, Analysis, and Software in Heliophysics (DASH)* among others
2. topical workshops, like those of the *space missions* exploited by **SPEARHEAD**.

The main dissemination channels for non-scientist audience are the project website, established at <https://spearhead-he.eu/> (Figure 4-1), its social media accounts (facebook¹, X/twitter², instagram³, Youtube⁴) as well as the news (<https://spearhead-he.eu/news/>) section (see also D8.1). Public talks and school visits will also disseminate the results to wider public.

Figure 4-1 - Home page of SPEARHEAD

¹ <https://www.facebook.com/spearhead.he>

² https://twitter.com/spearhead_he

³ <https://www.instagram.com/spearhead.he/>

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/@SpearheadHorizon-Europe>

5 Communication activities per Key Target Group

Specific communication activities targeted to the scientific user groups include the following events organized by **SPEARHEAD**:

- **Workshop 1** (Athens, Month 5–6): This is the first face-to-face meeting of the consortium brings together the participants, the international advisory board, and selected experts in the field to present and discuss the project goals and plans and the first results.
- **Workshop 2** (Rome, Month 18): Will bring in experts of the field to discuss SPEARHEAD results and kick off the user engagement on a larger scale.
- **Workshop 3 & School** (Kiel, Month 30-31): will bring in all teams and the advisory board, as well as young scientists outside the consortium. It will include a tutorial workshop on SPEARHEAD tools and data.

All meetings will be organized as hybrid events so that the community at large can participate. The number of on-site participants will be limited to 30–50 depending on the meeting; partial travel support for participants outside the consortium has been included in the budgets of the project. All scientific presentations will be recorded and then posted in the Youtube channel of the project. In addition to these events, we will organize webinars to promote our analysis tools. Those will be advertised in X/Twitter, instagram, facebook, the news section of SPEARHEAD’s website (Figure 5-1) and various newsletters of the scientific communities involved with **SPEARHEAD (T1, T3 and T4)**.

All the scientific results published as *peer-reviewed articles* will be *advertised with posts* on our X/Twitter feed, instagram and facebook channels to our peers (**T1, T2, T3, T4**).

Specific communication activities targeted to **University students** in the partner institutes and Europe-wide (**T4**) include:

- We will provide updated learning material for a 5-credit-point M.Sc. course on Solar Eruptions. The course will be given in May 2025 at UTU as a hybrid-mode course, allowing remote participation by students from European universities. The course will include input from the first results of the project and make use of the analysis tools that are under development at the time.
- In addition to the user workshops to be organised as Europe-wide events, we will also contribute to local Summer/Winter Schools at our host universities, targeted for undergrads, consisting of lectures and teamwork related to project themes.
- On the project website(s) we will publish blog posts/videos made by PhD students working in the project sharing their experiences and the science they are doing. These will be also shared in various social media channels.
- All partners will also make sure that the project and its results are visible at university-level research seminars and colloquia.
- We will also actively offer problems related to the project as topics for BSc and MSc theses as well as for student’s practice in our partner universities.

Specific **communication activities targeted to the Space Agencies and other policymakers (T5)** include:

Towards the end of the project, we will produce a White Paper on our results detailing the key observations that should be made in future solar missions in relation to relativistic SEPs and the remaining key open problems after the SPEARHEAD project. The paper will also address the problem from the point of view of data archives. The heliophysics community will be solicited for inputs in this effort.

Having PIs, co-PIs and co-Is of European heliophysics missions in the consortium (B. Heber, R. Vainio, R. Wimmer-Schweingruber, A. Rouillard), the consortium has direct involvement in the Science Working Groups of the key missions (Solar Orbiter, BepiColombo, SOHO) and ground-based facilities (NM stations; I. Usoskin, M. Laurenza) exploited in **SPEARHEAD**. All teams have close contacts with their national space administration.

Specific communication activities **targeted to the general public (T6)** include:

- Public talks and science events/festivals: We encourage all SPEARHEAD team members to actively engage in public outreach at the national level by giving public talks and organising events with a less formal format to engage the audience, e.g., panel discussions or interviews. We will also participate in international activities such as Researcher's Night which is hosted all around Europe.
- Image, movie and audio file gallery: **SPEARHEAD** webpage will host an image and movie gallery that includes a large amount of material compelling to the general public.
- Press releases: For most important results, press releases will be made (with the help of university/institute communication personnel). These are likely to result in stories in newspapers/journals, radio and TV interviews that can reach wide audiences, so that the information reaches the public in national languages.
- Blog posts/News: The key results/events will be published on our webpage as concise and general-level news/blog posts, which are also promoted on social media (e.g., Twitter, Instagram).
- YouTube channel: A YouTube channel has been established for communicating to the general public. We plan to make short videos, e.g., on key results of the project and its activities (e.g., science events, workshops)
- School visits: We will also encourage **SPEARHEAD** participants to visit schools and/or organise teacher training events to inform of topics related to Sun and space missions.

As detailed here above, **SPEARHEAD** will deliver enhanced targeted collaboration carefully addressing the broad scientific community. In particular, the planned Workshops of the project (organized in hybrid mode), involve the largest possible community representatives with experts and users being present (either on site or virtual). Additionally, videos of the scientific talks will be distributed via the Youtube channel of the project. Furthermore, the proposed webinars will be advertised to the broader community via the communication stream of SPEARHEAD and interested users will have access to publicly open demonstration.

Figure 5-1 – The News section of SPEARHEAD’s webpage

6 Conclusions

We outlined the expected results of the **SPEARHEAD** project and presented the first version of a detailed plan for dissemination and communication to target audiences. The plan will be a living document and will be updated over the project for each of the periodic reviews as well as for the final review

References

D1.2 Data Management Plan, 30-06-2024, SPEARHEAD Deliverable

D6.1 SPEARHEAD Tools and Data Development Plan, 30-06-2024, SPEARHEAD Deliverable

D8.1 Project Website, 29-02-2024, SPEARHEAD Deliverable

List of Acronyms/Abbreviations

Acronym/ Abbreviation	Description
ADS	Astrophysics Data System
AGU	American Geophysical Union
B.Sc.	Bachelor of Sciences
CME	Coronal Mass Ejection
Co-Is	Co-Investigators
Co-PIs	Co-Principal Investigators
COSPAR	Committee on Space Research
ECRS	European Cosmic Ray Symposium
EGU	European Geosciences Union
ESA	European Space Agency
ESPM	European Solar Physics Meeting
ESWW	European Space Weather Week
EU	European Union
IAGA	International Association of Geomagnetism and Aeronomy
IUGG	International Union of Geodesy and Geophysics
M.Sc.	Master of Sciences
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
NMs	Neutron Monitors
Ph.D.	Doctorate of Philosophy
PI	Principal Investigator
SEP	Solar Energetic Particle
SOHO	Solar and Heliospheric Observatory
SPEARHEAD	SPEcification, Analysis & Re-calibration of High Energy pArticle Data